

A Comparative Study of Observe Fasting and Non-Fasting Female Students on their Anxiety Level

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Abstract

This is a comparative study of observe fasting and non-fasting female students on their anxiety level. In this study 40 female participant were taken by non-probability of purposive sampling. Twenty female students who observed fasting in a week between the age of 18-25 and 20 female students who didn't observe fast between the same age group. Sinha's Comprehensive Anxiety test is prepared by A.K.P. Sinha and L. N. K. Sinha. It was administrated on both groups, and then data was analyzed by t-test. It was observed that significant level of the t-test is 0.02 and 0.05 it shows that there is significant difference between observe fasting and non-fasting female students on their anxiety level.

Key words: fasting, non-fasting female students, Anxiety

Introduction

For appropriate management of our life and multi-dimensional development of our personality Indigenous techniques are most important. Fasting is behavioral approach of Indigenous technique in psychotherapy it is help to manage our disturb life style. Fasting means upwas in Hindi, most people will treat it a way to keep yourself distance from food they think that by punishing the body they are pleasing to God but the main thing is that it an effective treatment or technique of relishing anxiety or stress and we got that how to manage our life style in a proper direction.

Fasting affects our physical, mental, spiritual, and emotional health of our body. Firstly it purifies our digestive system and allow for cleansing and detoxification of the

body. When food is scarce our bodies release chemicals to help protect our brains from the negative effects. These chemicals can put us in a good mood, and give a physical strength to our body.

Fasting improves mental clarity and focus to in our life with the greater freedom, flexibility, and energy to get done everything in your life. It gives us feeling lighter, more energetic, more enthusiastic, and requiring less sleep. By fasting we can improved concentration, attention and decrease our anxiety and stress level with better sleeping and make more refreshed to our day to day life.

In the perspective of Indian psychology disturbed emotions are the root Cause of our neurotic or psychotic disorders, in this case fasting is a medium of cleansing our emotions or a technique of purifying our emotions. Emotions are subjective feeling and fasting is gives positive direction to our feelings. Fasting can provide a way to clarify our emotional and mental aspect of life.

In the spiritual connection fasting gives us a very powerful effect by which we can give attention to our inner world and because of that in the future we can feel our inner voice in any situation. It gives quite quality and great sense of our inner being.

Between fasting periods we use to concentrate Meditation and pray to God by which we can imbibe our spiritual energy and level and make possible through which we can spread love and happiness in our entire surrounding world. It gives us an intuitive power to feel the humanity and positive feeling of the world.

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Train like a man, but like a women (Lauren Brooks of on Edge fitness) women of all type of ages heave taken the leap from weak to strong. A study found by Stefani Ruper, 2013 who wrote an incredible on her blog about fasting for women, showed that there are significant physiological changes for females that take place with calorie restriction and fasting. A research is shows in 2012-13 that fasting boosts the level of available serotonin in the brain which reduce migraine headaches and anxiety level.

In this study Sinha's Comprehensive Anxiety test which is described by A.K.P. Sinha and L.N.K. (1995) is used for testing the level of anxiety between 18-25 age group of female students who observed fast and non-fasting. Fasting an overcoming stress- by Ron Lagerquist 2014 says in the of Freedom you that "with in the first 24 hours of fast, my metabolism slowed down and the muscles in my neck begin to soften" Anxiety is a psychotic condition of heightened sensitivity to some perceived threat, risk, peril or danger. It is an emotion characterised by apprehension and anticipation of future danger or misfortune accompanied by feeling of dysphonia or somatic symptoms of tension. (American Psychiatric Association, 2000.)

Research methodology

Participants

40 participants between the age group of 18 to 25 were selected from Dev Sanskriti Vishwavidyalaya, Hardwar Uttarakhand. All participants were female students are selected with the purposive sampling method. 20 participants are observing fast student and 20 participants are non-fasting students.

Research Design

Between groups, comparative group design was applied for study. All were included in

comparative group. In experimental group 20 participant were selected of observe fasting and in control group 20 participant were selected of non-fasting female student.

Tool

Sinha's comprehensive anxiety test was used for measurement of the leave of anxiety observe fasting and non-fasting female student. Designed by A. K. P. Sinha and L. N. K. Sinha (1995). It contains 90 items of two point scale yes or no. Scoring was done with the help of manual one mark for the positive statement (yes) and zero mark for the negative statement is given. Reliability of the test is 0.85 and Validity of test is 0.62.

Procedure

Step1- Participants were invited for this empirical research. The objective of the experiment were explained them

Step 2- 40 female participants were selected by using purposive sampling

Step 3- Sinha's comprehensive anxiety test was administered on all participants of observed fasting and non-fasting.

Step 4- After giving the proper instructions questionnaires are proved for fill up.

Step 5- After taken all the questionnaires scoring procedure is completed with the help of manual prepared by A.K.P. Sinha and L. N. K. Sinha.

Step 6- data was analysed by using mean, standard deviation of both groups and tested the significant difference between the means of both groups with the help of t-test.

Result

Mean, standard deviation, standard error of mean, standard error of the deviation and degree of freedom of both groups are shown in the table and graph.

Result-table

Description of statistical analysis	Observe fasting	Non-fasting
Mean	12.35	14.65
SD	14.47	16.21
N	20	20
S _{ED}		4.94
Df		38
t- stat		2.14
Significant Level	0.02 and 0.05	

Graph

Mean of observe fasting- 12.35

Mean of non-fasting- 14.65

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to see the effect of fasting on anxiety. The result have predicted that there is no significant difference between observe fasting and non-fasting female student on their anxiety level. But prediction is being wrong or null hypothesis is rejected. It's proofed that there is significant difference between observe fasting and non-fasting female student on their anxiety level. It shows that observed fasting female students anxiety level is low comparatively non fasting female student. So we can say that fasting is affect to anxiety. The significant level of this study is 0.02 and 0.05

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